

Importance of Didactic Monitoring in Educational Management

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Abstract: This article highlights the study of the important aspects of school management transformation, emphasizes the importance of a systematic approach to improve educational results; it is described that in order to ensure the effectiveness of the school management system, it is necessary to constantly evaluate and adapt, as well as consider the involvement of interested parties, the integration of technology, and the optimization of resources. It also explores the transformation of school management in the digital age, focusing on technology integration, digital literacy, and the challenges and opportunities associated with these changes.

Key words: didactic monitoring, digital era, school management transformation, efficiency improvement, quality of education

At present, changes in the management system are considered important in our republic, implemented through democratized management, e-management, innovative programs and projects. These changes are used to improve educational efficiency, develop cooperation between teachers, parents and students, and introduce new technologies. Changes in the management system in schools will continue to be important efforts aimed at increasing the quality of the education system and improving the experiences of students.

Transformation of school management is a comprehensive process aimed at improving the overall performance of an educational institution. This transformation will help improve academic performance, increase efficiency and increase stakeholder satisfaction. The key components of a successful school management change are:

- *Stakeholder Engagement:* A successful transformation requires the involvement of all stakeholders, including teachers, administrators, parents, and students. Open communication and feedback mechanisms in social networks are aimed at developing shared responsibility among stakeholders.
- *Technology integration:* Incorporating technology into school management systems can streamline processes and increase efficiency. Online platforms facilitate the development of personalized learning, data-driven decision-making and effective communication between stakeholders.
- *Optimizing resources:* Effective use of resources such as staff, infrastructure and finance contributes to a more sustainable and high-performing school. Transparent budgeting and resource allocation processes ensure efficient and fair use of resources.
- *Implementation:* may include adopting new teaching methodologies, developing a positive school culture, or updating curricula to better meet the needs of the 21st century.
- *Evaluation and adaptation:* Continuous evaluation of the school management system and identification of areas for improvement is important for making necessary changes, and regular evaluation of key performance indicators helps to measure progress indicators and make future decisions^[6].

Changes in the management system of general secondary schools will greatly contribute to the development of the education system, increase the quality of the education system of Uzbekistan and create opportunities for future generations. These changes offer unique, practical and effective approaches to schools that are different from traditional management systems. Analyzing the transformation of the management system in the schools of our country and their effective implementation is an important aspect of spiritual and educational renewal and improvement of the quality of education. These processes are carried out in order to raise a modern, educated and spiritually strengthened generation for the future of our country. At the same time, it is one of the important tools that ensures sustainable development, maximizes the potential of students and improves the quality of service of educational institutions.

The main reasons for changes in the management system in general secondary schools are the adaptation of the education system to international standards, the widespread introduction of modern technologies and innovations to all areas of society, and the strengthening of cooperation between teachers, parents and students and increasing their participation in decision-making, forming the financial and legal independence of educational institutions. These processes are carried out by creating wider opportunities for schools, developing cooperation between teachers and parents and students, automating the educational system and improving the management of financial resources^[4]

In the era of digitization, an important task of school management is to establish electronic communication between students, teachers and parents. This communication helps to monitor student learning, offer additional resources to teachers, and improve the quality of the learning process, encourage student collaboration, and expand opportunities for student learning.^[2] Another important direction of school management in the era of digitization is the use of computer technologies and the internet to improve the professional skills of teachers and school employees, to improve the professional competence of teachers, to get acquainted with new technologies and methods, and to use them effectively in the teaching process^[3]. In addition, the educational system is used in order to increase the knowledge levels of students, develop professional competences of teachers, and strengthen cooperation between schools and educational institutions^[5].

At the same time, the use of new approaches to school management will help schools and educational institutions strengthen cooperation with external partners, expand resources, and improve the effectiveness of interaction between teachers and students. In the era of digitization, one of the important aspects of school management is focused on teaching taking into account the individual capabilities of students. This aspect ensures the flexibility of teaching methods, taking into account the differences and personal interests of students. It is important for schools and educational institutions to create a foundation for becoming successful individuals in social, economic and political life, providing students with the knowledge and skills to meet the new professional opportunities in the world and the demands of the labor market^[3]

As the world becomes digitally connected, and organizations increasingly operate across geographic boundaries, the concept of remote management is receiving a lot of attention. Remote or virtual management involves monitoring, coordinating and managing teams using digital communication tools to facilitate work processes^[10]. The need for remote management has increased due to global events such as the COVID-19 pandemic, which has forced a dramatic shift from traditional office settings to a remote work environment, redefining the way work is done and managed. Remote management requires unique leadership skills, strategies and tools to handle the complexities of managing a team without physical contact on a daily basis. This requires building trust, enhancing communication, leveraging technology, managing remote work, and building team cohesion. Effective communication is essential in a remote work environment. Remote managers must create clear lines of communication, ensuring their team members understand the organization's goals and specific roles. In addition, proficient use of digital tools

is a necessity for effective remote management. This includes communication tools like Zoom and Microsoft Teams, project management tools like Asana, and even virtual reality technology for remote collaboration^[12].

Finally, the administrative staff should pay attention to the results of the pedagogues' activities while controlling the work processes. With physical involvement lacking, leaders must create a results-oriented work environment and ensure that team members have a clear understanding of their duties and the quality of work expected. The use of remote control systems varies from country to country due to factors such as technological progress, cultural dynamics, and legal frameworks. Although the widespread use of distance education and monitoring technology in general education schools in the era of digitization is inextricably linked with management transformation, it cannot be said that it will be fully implemented in all aspects. The participants of the educational process are not yet ready to use distance education, the students and their parents are not ready to take more responsibility than in the traditional form of education, the teachers and the school. The main reasons can be cited as the lack of skills of administrative staff to use distance learning and to understand its possibilities. Studying the effectiveness of distance education technology and incorporating it into the education management system was introduced in 2006 in the education system of the Gatchina municipal district of the Leningrad region through the BlackBoard platform. Determining the effectiveness, efficiency, and appropriateness of education through remote management; pedagogical monitoring is necessary to collect and process status indicators of the pedagogical process, which provides forecasting and correction of its development.

A.S. Belkin lists the following types of pedagogical monitoring:

1. didactic – observing different aspects of the educational process;
2. educational – observation of various aspects of the educational process that takes into account the communication system of relations, the character of the interaction of the participants of the educational process;
3. management – observing the nature of interaction at different levels of management in systems;
4. socio-psychological – to observe the nature of the collective-group, personal relationship system, the psychological environment of the community, groups.

Conclusions about the effectiveness and relevance of the use of the selected pedagogical technology in a modern school in the conditions of the use of distance education technology will help to implement didactic and management control.

Didactic monitoring is monitoring of the implementation of educational, educational and developmental educational goals. Didactic monitoring is aimed at analyzing the internal side of the educational process from the point of view of its external aspects. In this case, the teacher provides knowledge through a remote resource. So, at this stage, various materials and lesson schedules of electronic study guides compiled by the tutor for the purpose of organizing distance lessons, including the reception of information by students, become an object of didactic monitoring.

Management monitoring – monitoring the nature of the interaction of the participants of the educational process using distance education at different levels of management in the systems. The purpose of such monitoring is to evaluate the effectiveness of the use of distance education technology from the point of view of ensuring the quality of education and collect materials for making management decisions^[1]

Due to the availability and increasing use of digital tools and technologies, school management has undergone significant changes. Technology integration in school management has been a key factor in transformation in the digital age. Schools have adopted a variety of digital tools to simplify administrative tasks, improve communication, and enhance the overall learning experience^[8]. Examples of such tools include LMS management systems, data management platforms, and online communication channels

(e.g., email, social media). These technologies have made schools more efficient, convenient, and responsive to the needs of students and staff.

Digital literacy plays a crucial role in transforming school management in the digital age. Teachers and administrators need to be proficient in using digital tools and resources to effectively manage their schools and support student learning^[11]. In addition, developing digital literacy among students equips them with essential 21st century skills and enables them to fully participate in a technology-driven society^[7]

There are not only opportunities but also potential challenges in integrating technology into school management. One challenge is to ensure equitable access to digital resources and connectivity for all students and staff. Another challenge is the need for ongoing professional development to ensure teachers and administrators are well equipped to use digital tools effectively. On the other hand, opportunities include the potential for increased productivity, improved communication, and personalized learning experiences^[9].

In conclusion, in the era of digitization, it is necessary to reflect the state of education in an educational institution through effective information, analytically generalize the results, develop a forecast for the development of the quality of education, and thereby changes in school management, new approaches, sustainable development of the education system, the effectiveness of communication between students, teachers and parents is of great importance to be integrated with modern technologies and innovations and remote management requires unique leadership skills and strategies to ensure effectiveness. As the telecommuting trend continues to grow, remote management will continue to be an important part of organizational management.

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